

Preparation of Some 1,2,3,4-Tetrazoles

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The reaction of nitrous acid with 4-alkyl- or 4-aryl-3-thiosemicarbazides produced the corresponding 5-substituted amino-1,2,3,4-thiatriazoles. On heating with aqueous bases, the thiatriazoles isomerised to yield the 1-substituted-1,2,3,4-tetrazole-5-thiols. Their ir and uv spectra were studied. The compounds have been found to possess antibacterial activity.

1,2,3,4-TETRAZOLES are well-known for their varied spectrum of pharmacological activities¹. The compounds are claimed to possess anti-convulsant², radioprotective³ and spermatostatic⁴ properties. In continuation of our studies on 1,2,3,4-tetrazoles as potential drugs, we have synthesised some new 1-substituted-1,2,3,4-tetrazole-5-thiols (Tables 1-3).

Freund and Hempel⁵ reported in 1895, that 4-substituted thiosemicarbazide(I) leads to the 5-substituted amino-1,2,3,4-thiatriazole(II) when treated with nitrous acid. This has been studied by ir and uv absorption spectra. The reaction of the 5-substituted amino-1, 2, 3, 4-thiatriazoles with aqueous bases results in isomerization to 1-substituted-1,2,3,4-tetrazole-5-thiols(III).

The uv spectra of the thiatriazoles(II) exhibit a characteristic absorption maxima at around 260-275 nm. The ir spectra of these compounds show the characteristic absorption bands at 2885, 1660, 1610, 1115, 945 and 935 cm⁻¹. The bands at 960-930 cm⁻¹ and 1160-1115 cm⁻¹ are common in these compounds as characteristic absorption for the thiatriazole ring system¹⁰.

The uv spectra of the tetrazoles(III) with different substituents showed similarities in having

TABLE 1—THIOSEMICARBAZIDES OF THE TYPE

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{R}-\text{NH}-\text{C}-\text{NHNH}_2 \\ \parallel \\ \text{S} \\ \text{(I)} \end{array}$$

R = Different groups

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C
1.	-C ₆ H ₁₁	142
2.	-2,6(OH) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	204
3.	-C ₆ H ₅	182
4.	-3NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃	103
5.	-α-C ₁₀ H ₇	80
6.	-3Cl.C ₆ H ₄	125
7.	-4HO.C ₆ H ₄	158
8.	-4OC ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄	176
9.	-2ClC ₆ H ₄	199

Note: There is good agreement with percentage of nitrogen and sulphur required and found.

TABLE 2—THIATRIAZOLES OF THE TYPE

R = Different groups

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C		Interpretation of zone of inhibition	
		Found	Reported	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	-CH ₃	90	96	-	-
2.	-C ₆ H ₅	66	66-7	-	-
3.	- <i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	40	40-41	+	-
4.	- <i>n</i> -C ₇ H ₁₅	75	75-75.5	+	-
5.	-C ₆ H ₅	143	142-43	+	-
6.	-4CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	139	140-44	++	-
7.	-2CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	116	120	+	-
8.	-4OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	140	136-37	+	-
9.	-2OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	91	89-90	+	-
10.	-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₅	78	80-81	-	-
11.	-4Cl.C ₆ H ₄	148	147-48	+	-
12.	-3Cl.C ₆ H ₄	189	-	++	-
13.	-2Cl.C ₆ H ₁₁	163	-	+	-
14.	-C ₆ H ₁₁	101	-	++	-
15.	-α-C ₁₀ H ₇	95	-	+	-
16.	-2,6(OH) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	90	-	++	+
17.	-3NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	141	-	-	-
18.	-4HOO.C ₆ H ₄	145	-	+	-
19.	-4OC ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄	122	-	+	+
20.	-3CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	154	-	++	-

+ indicates zone diameter less than 20 mm.
++ indicates zone diameter more than 20 mm.
- indicates no inhibitory zone.

characteristic absorption maxima at around 305 nm. The ir spectra of these compounds showed the characteristic absorption bands at 1300-950 cm⁻¹ and 760-740 cm⁻¹ which are common in these compounds. The region 760-740 cm⁻¹ is characteristic of 4 adjacent benzenoid H atoms¹¹.

All the compounds have shown good antibacterial activities against *Staphylococcus aureus* [Gram (+)ve] and poor activities against *Escherichia coli* [Gram (-)ve] according to the method adopted by Bauer-Kirby *et al*¹².

Experimental

Preparation of 4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazide: Aniline (0.1M; 9.3 g) was dissolved in liq. NH₃ (20

TABLE 3—TETRAZOLES OF THE TYPE

R = Different groups

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C		Ref. No.	Interpretation of zone of inhibition	
		Found	Reported		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	148	147-50	5	+	-
2.	-4CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	149	150-51	7	++	+
3.	-2CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	125	129	8	+	+
4.	-3CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	173	—	—	+	—
5.	-4OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	160	150	9	+	—
6.	-2OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	188	189-40	9	—	—
7.	-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	141	138-39	9	+	—
8.	-4ClC ₆ H ₄	157	156-57	9	+	—
9.	-3ClC ₆ H ₄	149	—	—	++	—
10.	-2ClC ₆ H ₄	179	—	—	—	—
11.	-C ₆ H ₁₁	203.5	—	—	—	—
12.	-α-C ₁₀ H ₇	207	—	—	+	—
13.	-n-C ₈ H ₉	60(d)	—	—	—	—
14.	-2,6(OH) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	205	—	—	++	—
15.	-3NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃	152	—	—	—	—
16.	-4HOC ₆ H ₄	160	—	—	++	—
17.	-4OC ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	205	—	—	++	—
18.	-n-C ₇ H ₁₅	—	—	—	—	—

(d) = decomposed.

(1) There is good agreement with percentage of nitrogen and sulphur required and found.

(2) + indicates zone diameter less than 20 mm.

++ indicates zone diameter more than 20 mm.

- indicates no inhibitory zone.

ml) and CS₂ (8 ml) was added with stirring, keeping the temperature below 30°. Ethanol (25 ml, 95%) was added and the stirring continued for half an hour. The contents were allowed to stand for two hrs and a solution of sodium chloroacetate (0.1M; 12.6 g) was added followed by hydrazine hydrate (10.0 ml, 50%), warmed and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to half its volume and allowed to stand overnight. It was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (95%); yield 13.61 g, 81.48%; m.p. 132°.

Preparation of 5-anilino-1,2,3,4-thiatriazole: To a stirred and cooled mixture of 4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (0.05M; 8.35 g) and hydrochloric acid (38.0 ml, 15%) was added sodium nitrate (0.05M, 3.45 g) in 25 ml of water at 10-15° over 40 mins. The white solid material, which rapidly turned pale pink, was filtered, dried and crystallised from mixture of ether-petroleum ether; yield 8.0 g, 89.0%; m.p. 143°(d).

Preparation of 1-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrazole-5-thiol: A mixture of 5-anilino-1,2,3,4-thiatriazole (0.012M; 2.2 g) and aqueous sodium hydroxide (4 moles, 25 ml, 10%) was refluxed for 30 mins and cooled. On acidification with hydrochloric acid at low temperature, hydrogen sulphide was liberated and a faint yellow crystalline material precipitated. It was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (95%); yield 1.0 g, 50%; m.p. 148°.

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